

Brian Paul Kaess
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Purpose: Seeking a position as an amateur Genealogist/Historian or ESL Teacher.

Education:

Lane Tech College Prep H.S., Chicago, Illinois, USA. Student from 1981-1985 GPA: 2.58, class of '85

Activities: Captain, Marine Fitness Team, Gamers Guild, Gymn Aide, Fro-Soph Basketball Team. Received 4th place individual Trophy in Chicago-area Marine Fitness Team competition. Print Shop, French Appreciation, German. Attended 20th Annual Reunion in Rosemont, Illinois, in 2005.

A.S. degree in General Studies, 2.97 GPA
Northern Virginia Community College, Woodbridge, Virginia.
Attendance from March 1986- August 1987

Undergraduate Study, Study in History, GPA: 3.5
University of Texas at San Antonio, San Antonio, Texas
Attendance from May 1989-February 1990

B.A. *cum laude* degree Major in Philosophy, Minor in History, GPA: 3.63
Northeastern Illinois University, Chicago, Illinois
Attendance from Fall 1988-May 1993, degree awarded in May 1992.
Graduate Study in History. Activities: Vice-President, Philosophy Club, Student Aide, Veterans Office & Foreign Student Office. Left in good standing.

Graduate Study, Philosophy, GPA: 3.33
Northern Illinois University, Dekalb, Illinois.
Attendance from Fall 1993- May 1995
Left in good standing.

Work/Employment:

Mings Chop Suey, Chicago, Illinois.
Bicycle Delivery Boy
About Fall 1982-Spring 1983

Lebanese Restaurant, Chicago, Illinois.
Dishwasher
About Spring 1984-Summer 1984

Edgewater Hospital, Chicago, Illinois.
Pageboy
July 1984-July 1985

Jewel-Osco, Inc., Chicago, Illinois.
Bagger
About Spring 1988-August 1988

Kane Security Service, Inc., Chicago, Illinois.
Security Guard
Fall 1988-Spring 1989

Stanley Smith, Inc., San Antonio, Texas.
Security Guard
Spring 1989-February 1990

Special Operations Associates, Inc., Chicago, Illinois.
Security Guard
February 1990-October 1991

Edgewater Medical Center, Chicago, Illinois.
Emergency Room Registration Clerk
June 1992-September 1996

Direct Response Corporation, Inc., Glenview, Illinois.
Inbound Communicator
May 1994-January 1995

E.T.S. Foreign Language Institute, Pusan, South Korea
English Conversation Instructor
September 1996-March 1997
One-Year Korean ESL Teaching Visa/resident card granted.

Joliet Central H.S., Joliet, Illinois
Substitute Physics Teacher
November 1998

Taught various sections of Physics, including an Honors section, for one day. I held an Illinois Substitute Teaching License for this job from the ISBE. Joliet Central H.S. is where my sister-in-law Robin (Brown) Kaess' mom had attended school back in the 50's or so.

Gordon Tech Catholic High School, Chicago, Illinois. Registrar
November 1998-June 2001

Activities: Asst. Coach, Speech & Debate Team, judged at the Illinois State Speech & Debate Finals in Springfield, Illinois, in 2001. Asst. Coach, Chess Club. Taught Freshman Literature.

Truman College, City Colleges of Chicago, Chicago, Illinois.
ESL Instructor in Adult Education Dept.
December 1998-May 2002

I think I received an Illinois ESL Endorsement because I already had relevant teaching experience abroad, and a substitute teaching license in Illinois. My boss Ruth Lambach put me in for the endorsement. Various ESL teaching workshops at Navy Pier.

Evanston Northwestern Healthcare, Skokie, Illinois.
Patient Service Representative III
August 2001-December 2001
PSR III Certificate.

Dist. 214 Adult Education, Mt. Prospect, Illinois.
ESL/Computer Skills Instructor
August 2001-December 2001

Baejae Institute, Ulsan, South Korea.
English Conversation Instructor
May 2002-october 2002

Daley College, City Colleges of Chicago, Chicago, Illinois.
ESL Instructor in Continuing Education Dept.
September 2003-September 2003

American Historical Society of Germans from Russia (AHSGR), Lincoln, Nebraska.
Village Coordinator (volunteer)
2024-2025

Military Service:

U.S. Army

Medic

July 1985-April 1988

Parachute Badge, ASR,AAM, Superior Performance Certificate

Honorable Discharge

Illinois Army National Guard

Medic

April 1988-January 1989

Honorable Discharge

U.S. Marine Corps

Mortarman, Radio Operator

March 1997- October 1998

Overseas Service in Cuba

Honorable Discharge

U.S. Disabled Veteran (10%)

Certificates/Activities:

Basic Computer Literacy Certificate

Truman College, Continuing Education Dept.

2001

Deutsche Welle (DW) German Zertificat B1 Level

2019

Spanish Language Courses

Spanish Horizons Language School, Chicago, Illinois.

Summer 2005

Church Activities:

First Evangelical Free Church (EFCA), Chicago, Illinois.

Youth Basketball Team, Chicago-area Conference Title 1982

1982-1985

University Bible Fellowship (UBF), Chicago, Illinois & Pusan, South Korea.

Missionary (volunteer)

1990-1997

Associations:

Sons of Confederate Veterans (SCV) 2011-2013

Military Order of Stars and Bars (MOSB) 2012-2014

Germanic Genealogy Society (GGS) 2018-2023

Mid-Atlantic Germanic Society (MAGS) 2017-2018

Southwest Florida Germanic Genealogy Society (SWFLGGS (2019-2020) (now defunct)

Polish Genealogical Society of America (PGSA) 2016-2017

American Historical Society of Germans from Russia (AHSGR) 2024-2025

American Veterans for Ukraine (2024-2026)

Publications:

See articles by Brian Paul Kaess in *Rodziny, Germanic Genealogy Journal, Edgewater Scrapbook, Polish Eaglet, Journal of the American Historical Society of Germans from Russia, Kansas Review, News & Views, & Das Posthorn.*

See family books by Brian Paul Kaess such as *Kaess/Ochiltree/Swartz family History (2017)* & *Kaess Family from the Neckar Valley (2019)*

See Letters to the Editor by Brian Paul Kaess in the *San Antonio Express-News, Northern Star, & Der Kurier.*

See academic/family history articles by Brian Paul Kaess published online at Zenodo.org, as well as content at Pinterist, etc.

Hobbies:

Genealogy/Local History

Travel

Light Fitness

Pets

Food